

INNOVATIVE PROCESSES IN EDUCATION

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Annotation. In recent years, a number of new concepts from other fields have entered the theory of pedagogy. This indicates that pedagogy is related to other disciplines. Most of the concepts came from the fields of technology and economics, which are the basis for the development of human thought.

Keywords: education, opinion, innovation, computerization, situation, discipline, agriculture, manufacturing.

Today, various opinions are expressed about the economics and improvement of education, the teacher and teaching techniques and technologies, the economy of education, computerization of teaching.

Although it is not clear when the word "innovation - newness" appeared, there are opinions that this concept entered the general sciences, from the natural sciences. Most of these innovations were introduced in the fields of agriculture, manufacturing and medicine. As a pedagogical term, the concept of innovation is one of the new concepts, and various definitions and opinions are given to it.

Innovation has been changing since the dawn of society. Some pedagogues use the word innovation in a narrow sense to improve and modernize education, while others give it a broader meaning. Some new concepts in the field of education are being replaced by reform, modernization, improvement, and optimization of teaching.

We will focus on the definitions given to innovation as a pedagogical concept.

French scientist E. Brunswick shows three types of pedagogical innovation:

1. completely new, previously non-existing ideas and actions appear as innovation.;
2. most innovations require adapting, expanding or changing ideas and actions at a certain time, in a certain environment;
3. Pedagogical innovations happen depending on the situation. These innovations revitalize existing activities and ensure the effectiveness of ideas based on re-purposed by changing requirements.

American Beal and Bolen define pedagogical innovations as "complex innovation in views and application, not just innovation involving changes in material." Changes and complex changes are defined here.

Nayhoff describes news as a process: "This process begins with an idea and influences its transformation, and ends with consumer acceptance or rejection."

Marklund explains the difference between innovation and change as follows: "The concept of innovation is used in school and in the educational process in a similar way to the word change. If this change involves the school system, it is considered a reform. But not every change is new. The innovation should ensure the achievement of the previously set goal. Innovation always creates one or more qualitative criteria.

In the general encyclopedia, the concept of innovation is defined as "new, renewal, novelty - the implementation of technical and technological discoveries and achievements."

In special and pedagogical literature, innovation is defined differently by authors dealing with this problem.

Uzbek scientist, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor N.N.Azizkhojaeva defines the word innovation and admits the following: "Innovation" (in English innovation) is innovation.

Innovation is both an internal logic and a dynamic system that develops legitimately over time and expresses its interaction with the environment.

Innovation in scientific fields is directly: a new method, methodology, technology, etc.

In the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, the word innovation is explained as follows: "innovation - English innovationas - is an introduced innovation, invention, innovations, activities in the fields of technique, technology, management and skill organization based on scientific and technical achievements and best practices. application in the scopes" is indicated. (Uzbekistan national encyclopedia State scientific publishing house. Tashkent 2002, page 169)

"Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and teacher's and student's activities, and in its implementation mainly interactive methods are fully used." (R.J. Ishmuhamedov. Ways to increase the effectiveness of education with the help of innovative technologies. -T. 2004. p. 3)

Regarding innovation and change, some define innovation, others as quantitative change, and a third category of people as qualitative change.

In the period of socio-economic reforms, the introduction of innovations into the life of the society ensures improvement of human labor and comfort. Also, the need for innovation requires a number of changes in the field of education.

A student or pupil comes to the educational institution to get knowledge, and the teacher organizes the educational process by looking for the most convenient and effective ways to impart knowledge to the student. In order for pedagogues to work successfully and educate students, they must know how to apply innovations to the educational process. That is why the term innovation has attracted the attention of many people. Now, in order to fully and accurately apply innovation in education, it is necessary to understand its content and essence. It takes some time.

Schoolchildren strive to express themselves as individuals. For this, they begin to take up various types of activities. It is important that teachers also try to realize all the possibilities of the student during the educational process.

The process of teaching through innovation optimizes the interaction between the teacher and the student. It is envisaged that both people will become active participants.

The effectiveness of the educational process depends, of course, on the nature of these interactions.

If the educational process is organized at a high level through innovation, future specialists will show intellectual activity. Intellectual activity helps the future specialist to prepare in every way, to become a master of the future activity. Intellect (Latin intellectus - that is, intelligence, perception, mind) means. This means forming a person's cognitive activity, thinking in a narrow sense, the process of thinking.

The task of modern pedagogy requires the application of innovations in the educational process to increase the intellectual activity of students. Because today the introduction of innovations in the educational process has a good effect. Therefore, it is necessary to classify (classify) the innovation used in the educational process.

Innovations in the field of education require innovations and changes in education, improvement and improvement of existing ones. That's why there are always some changes in the educational process.

The current period can be called a period of great and rapid changes in the field of education, as well as in all areas of society. There are different views of news. Types of news are separated mainly for methodological reasons.

Fields of education are so closely related that innovations in one field lead to innovations in any other field. Therefore, the introduction of innovations in some components of education requires determining the overall effectiveness of the innovations used.

When classifying innovations of the educational process, it is necessary to take into account that innovation is one of the important manifestations of human activity. This activity is free from serious boundaries and divisions. It is difficult to include all the concepts and aspects of the educational process in the novelty and embody them in one concept. Innovation affects its methodology and technology in the process of organizing educational content. However, it is necessary to classify the innovation used in the educational process.

In our opinion, the first main criterion depends on the environment in which the innovation will be introduced. The second criterion is the ways of applying the innovation, the third is the breadth and depth of the innovation implementation measures, and the fourth criterion is the reason for the creation of the innovation.

Depending on the field of education in which innovations are introduced and applied, the following innovations can be included in the first criterion: 1) in the content of education, 2) in technology, 3) in organization, 4) in the management system. Depending on the ways of introducing innovations they can be divided into the following:

- a) systematic, planned, premeditated;
- b) unexpected, spontaneous, sudden. Irrespective of the breadth and depth of the activities of introduction of news, the following types can be listed:
 - a) public, large, global, systematic, acute, reasonable, important, serious, deep, etc.;
 - b) partially, small, tiny.

Depending on the nature of the news, they can be combined as follows: a) external and b) internal.

The above-mentioned features determine a high level of interest of the learner, as a result of which the effectiveness of the educational process increases.

Education based on the introduction of news is highly effective in the following cases:

- 1) when based on factors of personal interest. Students will be responsible for the learning process because they know their needs well.
- 2) when responding to primary needs. Education will be based on students' primary needs, and the pursuit of learning will be high.
- 3) when students' involvement is ensured.

Active participation in the learning process, not laziness.

4) based on independent opinion.

The learning process is most effective when it is based on independent thinking; students learn from each other.

5) when providing feedback.

Effective learning requires both guiding and supportive feedback.

7) when showing respect for students.

Mutual respect and trust between the coach and the student will help the learning process.

8) when a friendly environment is created.

A student who is in a friendly mood will learn the material much more easily than a student who is scared, excited, or angry.

9) when a favorable situation occurs.

If the student is motivated to learn, he will learn the learning material quickly and easily.

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